

ESSENCE OF APPLICATION OF STATIC AND OPTIMIZATION METHODS OF FORECASTING IN ECONOMIC PROCESSES

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Abstract: The specific features of modeling economic processes in the conditions of a market economy are that the market has elements of risk and uncertainty, limited resources and the existence of competition between producers and consumers, the ability to foresee the future state of economic indicators, and the presence of asymmetric information in the market.

Key words: element, resources, dispersion, correlation, regression, factor analysis, economic-mathematical method, optimal programming method, static and dynamic, linear and non-linear, optimal.

The main economic-mathematical methods are the methods of mathematical statistics: dispersion analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis, factor analysis. Econometric methods, theory of economic growth, intersectoral balance, production function, demand and supply analysis. Optimal programming methods, linear programming, non-linear programming, stochastic programming, dynamic programming [1]. Methods related to market economy are free competition, production cycle model, models related to firms. Methods of experimental study of the economic system are simulations, business games, conducting scenarios. In a narrow sense, a model is an auxiliary object that reflects the important features and properties of the studied object, process or event, and in a broad sense, it is a sample of an object or a system of objects [2].

All models created using modeling methods can be divided into two types: material models and ideal models. Material models represent real objects using natural and artificial materials: making a model with chalk on a board, cardboard,

writing a formula with a pencil, making an airplane model out of metal. Ideal models are closely related to the human thinking process. Operations with such models are performed in the brain. One of the most widely used models in economics is economic-mathematical models [3]. Mathematical modeling is understood as representation of economic processes through equations, inequalities, functional, logical schemes. Mathematical modeling, in a broad sense, is a method of investigation and research that studies processes that are described by different, but similar, mathematical relationships. Economic-mathematical models can be functional and structural in their place. Functional models represent functions that link input and output parameters. Structural models are more complex, represent the internal structure of the system and reflect internal relationships [4]. Models can be static and dynamic, linear and non-linear, deterministic and stochastic. In static models, the state of economic processes and indicators at a certain time is studied. In dynamic models, how economic indicators change over time is observed and what factors affect them are studied. In linear models, the objective criterion is in the form of a linear function, the relationship between its extreme values is expressed by linear equations and inequalities [5]. In non-linear models - the relationship between the objective function and the solution is expressed in a non-linear form. Convex programming - the problem to be solved is given in a convex set, and the objective function can be given in convex form. Quadratic programming - the objective function is expressed in quadratic form, and the boundary conditions are given in the form of linear equations and inequalities [6]. Integer Programming - An integer is entered in a condition with respect to the variable being searched for. Dynamic programming - the solution of an extreme problem consists of several steps, and the solution of each previous step is used as initial data for the next steps. Optimal models serve to find the optimal option for organizing production. In other words, they can give a maximum or minimum value to the objective function according to the optimality criteria. Constraint systems or economic system change conditions and Optimality criteria (objective function). This criterion is used to determine the level of

efficiency of the possible state of the economic system, compare and choose the most favorable one. If the objective function represents a positive economic factor (for example, profit or income), then the maximum value of the objective function is sought, while in the case of cost minimization, it is necessary to seek the minimum of the objective function [7]. The set of numerical values of the unknowns is called the plan of the problem. Any plan that satisfies a set of constraints is called a feasible plan. A possible plan that can give the maximum (or minimum) value of the objective function is called the optimal plan. If the objective function and the unknowns included in the system of constraints are linear, then it is called linear programming. If the objective function or system of constraints consists of non-linear expressions, then it is called non-linear programming. Economic-mathematical model of the optimal programming problem in the canonical form. A general linear programming problem can be solved using two methods. The first of these is the simplex method or the method of successive improvement of the plan. The second method is the distribution method [8]. The main task performed by this method of linear programming is the transportation problem.

Data analysis is a branch of mathematics and computer science that deals with the construction and study of the most general mathematical methods and computational algorithms for obtaining knowledge from experimental data. Data analysis is the process of studying, cleaning, transforming and modeling data in order to obtain useful information and make decisions. Data mining is a specific method of data analysis that focuses on modeling and discovering data rather than describing it. In statistical terms, databases divide data analysis into descriptive statistics, exploratory data analysis, and statistical hypothesis testing. While organizational data analysis is concerned with discovering new features of the data, statistical hypothesis testing is concerned with confirming or rejecting existing hypotheses [9]. While predictive analytics focuses on applying statistical or systematic models for prediction or classification, text analytics applies statistical and systematic techniques to extract and classify information from textual sources

of unstructured data. These are all types of data analysis. Data integration is the foundation of data analysis, and data analysis itself is closely related to data dissemination. The term "data analysis" is sometimes used as a synonym for data modeling [10].

Systematic approach in economic analysis, as it is known, is a systematic approach in research methodology. It is based on qualitative study of a complex system consisting of elements consisting of a large number of internal and external connections. A systematic approach allows to study the object in depth and comprehensively, to have a complete idea about it, to determine the cause-and-effect relationships between its separate units. The main feature of the systemic approach is the mutual influence, interdependence, mutual connection and dynamic nature of the elements of the system, complexity, integrity, subordination, separation of the leading link [11].

Systematic approach in economic analysis makes it possible to develop scientifically based options of economic issues and choose the most appropriate management decisions by calculating the effectiveness of these options [12].

In the systematic analysis, the process of its implementation can be divided into several successive stages.

The first stage. At this stage of the research, the object is considered as a certain system, and for this, separate parts, which are considered as elements of the system, are first separated. Also, the goals and objectives of the system development, relations with other systems, mutual connections between individual elements, operation of each element and the whole system are determined [13].

The second stage. The main goal of this stage is to select indicators that give a complete and qualitative description of all elements of the system, their interrelationships (external and internal), conditions of its existence.

The third stage. The main goal of this stage is to develop a general drawing of the studied system. Graphically, it consists of individually structured blocks, where each element corresponds to a separate block. Individual blocks are connected with arrows describing the presence and direction of connections between them.

The fourth stage. This stage is devoted to the general economic mathematical model of the system. In this case, the mathematical expression of some equations and inequalities of the system is determined by means of qualitative analysis [14].

The fifth stage. At this stage, "working with the model" is carried out. It is recommended to work with the model in dialog mode. In working with the model, in our opinion, the use of simulation models is appropriate.

Methodology of comprehensive analysis. The use of the method of economic analysis is revealed through a number of specific methods of analytical research. It can be a method of applying individual aspects of economic activity, or it can be a method of complex research. It should be noted that each type of analysis has its own style. In general, style means a set of rules and methods of doing this or that work that are most suitable for the purpose.

Method in economic analysis means analytical methods and procedures for researching the economy of the enterprise, which are arranged in a certain way to achieve the goal of the analysis. The method of economic analysis can be conditionally divided into two groups. General and private methods. The general method is a research system that is used in the same way in the study of various objects of different branches of the national economy. Specific method-general method is determined according to a certain branch of the economy, a certain type of production or a certain object of research [15]. Conducting a complex economic analysis necessarily requires determining its procedure. The steps involved in performing a comprehensive economic analysis are shown separately. At the first stage, the object, purpose and tasks of the analysis are determined, the analysis plan is drawn up. In the second stage, synthetic and analytical indicators describing the object of analysis are developed. In the third stage, the information necessary for the analysis is collected and prepared. In the fourth stage, the results of economic activity are compared with the business plan, the previous year, and the indicators of advanced enterprises. At the fifth stage, factor analysis is carried out and the influence of factors on the resulting indicators is calculated. In the sixth stage, unused and promising opportunities for increasing production efficiency are

identified. At the seventh stage, the assessment of the economic activity is carried out, taking into account the influence of various factors and the identified unused opportunities, and specific measures for their use are determined. Performing analytical studies in such a sequence is appropriate from the theoretical and practical point of view of economic analysis. An important element of the complex economic analysis method is its technical methods [16]. These methods can be briefly called analytical instruments. They can be used at different stages of the analysis. The methods used in economic analysis are categorized differently. These are traditional methods of information processing, methods of deterministic factor analysis, methods of factor analysis, optimization of indicators are used in most cases. It can be seen that in the process of economic analysis, in addition to methods of information processing and calculation of general indicators, methods of factor analysis and optimization of indicators are widely used. Among these methods, the oldest and oldest are its traditional methods, which are widely used for data processing not only in economic analysis, but also in other disciplines. Traditional methods of economic analysis, comparison, calculation of relative quantities, calculation of average quantities, grouping, balance method, graphic method are described. The methods included in the traditional methods are also different. Here, along with methods of preliminary analysis (comparison, graphical representation, grouping) and methods of calculating general indicators (relative and average quantities), methods of factor analysis (balance connection method) are also included in its composition. Deterministic factor analysis methods mainly include factor analysis methods, including chain link, index, differences in absolute and relative quantities, integral and proportional methods. These are chain connection, index, differences in absolute quantities, integral, proportional distribution, differences in relative quantities. It can be seen that among the main methods used in deterministic factor analysis are the most widespread universal private methods of economic analysis (chain connection, differences in absolute and relative quantities, proportionality) economic-statistical (index) and mathematical (integral) methods are also included. Simulation modeling and

heuristic methods can also be added to the main methods of optimizing indicators used in economic analysis. As can be seen from the above, the methods used in the process of economic analysis are diverse and colorful. In the course of the analysis, keeping them on the basis of whether they have arrived or not, will definitely increase the number of analytical calculations and in some cases will lead to distortion of its results. Therefore, when choosing them, it is necessary to choose a method that corresponds to the essence of the economic problem to be solved [17].

Working of analytical indicators system. All objects of economic analysis are reflected in the system of indicators of business plans, accounts, reports and other data sources. It is known that any economic phenomenon or process is often determined not by a single, separate indicator, but by a complex of several interrelated indicators. In this regard, choosing and justifying a system of indicators to reflect economic phenomena and processes is an important methodological issue of economic analysis [18]. Grouping and systematization of a large number of different indicators used in economic analysis is of great importance. Indicators can be classified according to a number of signs, that is, according to their content, they are divided into quantitative and qualitative indicators, depending on the field of application, they are divided into general and special indicators, according to the level of synthesis, indicators are divided into generalizing, specific and auxiliary indicators, according to the method of obtaining, indicators are divided into absolute and relative indicators. in the study of cause-and-effect relationships, indicators are divided into factor and result indicators.

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